

Studies on soil engineering properties and stabilization of Purulia soil by chemical treatment with sodium salts

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Abstract : A systematic investigation was made on the modification of soil known as stabilization for improvement of the properties of soils by controlled chemical treatment. The studies were made on Purulia soil stabilization by chemicals like NaCl, Na₂SiO₃. Inferences regarding the stabilization were drawn from the comparison of the change in the soil index and engineering properties like the liquid limit (LL), plastic limit (PL), plasticity index (PI), compaction compression index, shear permeability and consolidation characteristics etc. of the stabilized soils vis-à-vis the normal soils. Sodium chloride was found to be ineffective and sodium silicate was found to be beneficial to some extent. It may be due to gel forming ability and stabilizing influence of sodium silicate. Physico-chemical interpretation has been given and inferences are drawn regarding the chemicals used for stabilization.

Keywords : Compaction, compression index, plastic index, Purulia soil.

Soils are the supporting medium for many forms of life and form the basis of agriculture and forestry¹⁻⁶. Soil also has a major role as an environment agent and it acts as a sink for chemicals from atmosphere, hydrosphere and biosphere. Soil acts as a filter for different aqueous and solid inputs from different sources¹⁻⁵.

But soil also provides the basic needs like housings, construction of roads and bridges for transportation and communication, construction of dams for water storage and supply, flood control, construction of factories, power houses to meet the basic needs of the modern and advance societies. Geotechnique is concerned with the study of soil, its behaviour and application as an engineering material⁷⁻⁹.

Little work has been reported on the soil engineering properties of West Bengal. Different soil properties like penetration tests, grain size, specific gravity, Atterberg limits etc. of the undisturbed soil samples collected from different locations of West Bengal were studied by Dedalal^{10,11}, Das and Parua¹² to understand their engineering properties mainly for construction purposes. However, controlled chemical treatment of soils known

as stabilization has been extensively used in developed countries to modify or to strengthen the soil characteristics and soil engineering properties¹³⁻¹⁵. Lime was used extensively. The strength of soil lime mixtures depend on soil type, lime content, type of lime, curing time, method of mixing, temperature, water content, pH and time lag between mixing and compaction. Impact of organic carbon, other chemicals and contaminants on soils was also reported¹⁶.

Soil stabilization and change in the engineering properties by lime, lime-fly ash and related aspects have been studied by Chakraborty, Dedalal and Nath^{17,18}, APERL, Hyderabad¹⁹, Shivapulliah²⁰, Sridharan and Ramesh²¹, Nath *et al.*²². Clough, Kuck and Kasali²³ reported the strengthening and stiffening of a cohesion-less sandy soils *in situ* by means of injection of a silicate solution that gels with time. It is a commonly used technique used in Europe and Japan to increase bearing capacity which minimizes movements around shallow tunnels in urban areas.

Lime is widely used for stabilization but CaCl₂ may also be used²⁴. Problem associated with leaching can be avoided if CaCl₂ (1%) is mixed with Na₂SiO₃ (1%). It is

accompanied by gel formation and increased strength of the expansive soil²⁴. Sadana²⁵ studied the creep behaviour of clay with calcium and sodium salts. Cyclic swell-shrink behaviour of expansive soil stabilized with lime and rice husk ash (RHA, SiO₂, Al₂O₃, CaO) was examined by Chandrasekhar *et al.*²⁶.

Studies on the stabilization of a Purulia soil by the controlled addition of Ca(OH)₂, CaCl₂ and Ca(NO₃)₂ have been reported recently by the authors²⁷.

The work has been extended to study the engineering properties in order to understand effect of controlled chemical treatment like sodium chloride and sodium silicate to a Purulia soil to improve and strengthen the soil characteristics as little is known regarding the effects of sodium salts to Indian soils. A comparison can also be made between the effect of sodium salts and calcium salts on the stabilization process. The results of the investigation are described in this paper.

Experimental

The silty clay used in the present investigation was collected from a proposed dam site in Purulia district (Western region of West Bengal). Disturbed soil sample was collected near the site from a dug pit. The specific gravity, grain size analysis, liquid limit (LL), plastic limit (PL), plasticity index (PI), cation exchange capacity (CEC) compaction, compression index (C_c) and undrained shear strength (C_u) were determined. Preparation of samples for different mechanical tests like sedimentation in the laboratory, Atterberg limit test, shear, permeability, consolidation, compaction test and other experimental details are similar to those described before²⁷. Consolidation, shear and permeability tests were carried out at optimum moisture content (OMC) using only Ca(OH)₂²⁷

and Na₂SiO₃.

Consolidation/sedimentation tests were carried out using soil samples in aqueous suspensions (blank) and salt solutions (at different concentrations).

Loss of concentration of salt solutions were measured by determining the difference in the concentrations of Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ ions in leached experimental and the blank solutions. Systronics Digital Flame Photometer (Model 125) and EDTA titrations were used to determine Na⁺-K⁺ and Ca²⁺-Mg²⁺ respectively.

Results and discussion

The silty (yellowish brown loamy) clay (having clay content 42.2%) used, is residual in origin¹⁰. The tract is well drained i.e. the soil has been formed under leaching and oxidising environments. Soil is expected to be composed of clay of base unsaturated type having little or no alluvial experience²⁷. The Purulia soil is known to be composed of mostly kaolinite with illite to some extent^{1,17}. The index properties are given before²⁷.

(A) *Atterberg limit values*^{17,20,21,30-33} :

Liquid limit, plastic limit and plasticity index, (LL-PL) values are 48.5, 20.5 and 28 respectively (Table 1). Results of Atterberg limit values of some of the chemically treated soil samples cured for 7 days have been given in Table 1.

Addition of Na⁺ (as NaCl) in Purulia soil decreases liquid limit values. More the salt concentration, less is the value of liquid limit (LL), but the effect is more pronounced in lower concentrations indicating that there is an optimum concentration of Na⁺ ion in this soil beyond which the phenomenon causing lowering of LL is not effective. The value of PL of the original soil is low and

Table 1. Atterberg's limits of the soil with and without chemical additives

Sl. no.	Soil details	Liquid Limit (LL)	Plastic Limit (PL)	Plasticity Index (PI) (LL - PL)
1.	Clay blank (Purulia soil)	48.5	20.5	28.0
2.	Soil + 0.8% Na ⁺ (as NaCl)	45.7	21.7	24.0
3.	Soil + 0.2% Na ⁺ (as NaCl)	44.8	20.8	24.0
4.	Soil + 0.4% Na ⁺ (as NaCl)	44.0	21.0	23.0
5.	Soil + 0.8% Na ⁺ (as NaCl)	43.5	21.5	22.0
6.	Soil + 1% Na ⁺ (as NaCl)	43.7	19.3	24.4
7.	Soil + 0.1% Na ⁺ (Na ₂ SiO ₃)	43.7	17.2	26.5
8.	Soil + 0.2% Na ⁺ (Na ₂ SiO ₃)	42.8	19.4	23.4
9.	Soil + 0.4% Na ⁺ (Na ₂ SiO ₃)	40.8	19.2	21.6
10.	Soil + 1.6% Na ⁺ (Na ₂ SiO ₃)	47.5	29.3	18.2

with salt addition no significant effect is noticed in the values of PL. However a tendency of lowering of PI is noticed.

Addition of Na⁺ (as Na₂SiO₃) to the soil makes it very sticky but there is very sharp decrease in LL value. This lowering goes on till the concentration is 0.8% and at higher concentration the value starts increasing and then nears the value of the original soil. The value of PL has become very low at a low concentration (0.1%), but it gradually increases and surpasses the value of the blank soil at a high concentration. PI decreases steadily and at the highest concentration it stops further decrease. In comparison to the soils added with Na⁺ (as NaCl) the soils (with Na₂SiO₃) show greater effect on the values of LL, PL, PI indicating a probable contribution of anion in the phenomenon. Na₂SiO₃ has gel forming capability and it will have more stabilizing influence than NaCl.

In a soil suspension tendency of flocculation is the result of increase of net attractive force and it may be caused by increasing ion concentration, ion valency etc. or by decreasing pH, size of hydrated ion, anion adsorption, dielectric constant etc.^{19,31}.

Salt addition normally causes depression of double layer. The result is that less amount of water is immobilized by the soil particles and hence it is expected that less water is required to reach the liquid limit state. The greater the salt concentration greater is this effect till the electrical capacity of the surface charges of the clay particles is satisfied. Then the particles with less thick double layer interact and probably flocculation phenomenon dominates and more water is required to reach the liquid limit state. This is possibly the cause of lowering of LL upto a maximum salt concentration beyond which the LL once again tends to increase.

The higher valency of a cation causes greater double layer depression compared to a lower valency cation³¹. This may be the cause of slightly greater effect with CaCl₂ in comparison with NaCl. Anion adsorption on the edges of clay particle has some contribution on the double layer size. So anion may be another factor affecting the changes of Atterberg limit values.

The effect on PL is slightly erratic, either the values are same or slightly reduced or the values gradually increase with the concentration of salts. The values of plasticity index i.e. the range over which the soil remains plastic is in a decreasing mode with the higher salt concentration. However the present test programme is limited to low concentrations of salts only. The Purulia clay is expected to be a mixture mainly of kaolinite and illite

and the activity value is rather poor.

$$\bar{A} = \frac{PI}{Clay\%} = \frac{28}{42.2} = 0.66$$

Unlike montmorillonite (which has a very high specific surface) kaolinite has less surface area. So the magnitudes of variation in the values of Atterberg limits are not high.

It may be inferred that the effects due to addition of salts on the Atterberg limit are mainly dependent on the clay (mineral, amount) and the salts type i.e. (cation, anion and concentration) and other factors like period of curing etc.

(B) Standard Proctor compaction test^{17,18} :

The test results have been given in Figs. 1A and 1B. Addition of Na₂SiO₃ makes the soil sticky, max. dry density has been reduced to some extent and the OMC has been increased.

Fig. 1. Standard Proctor compaction test results.

In the case of sodium silicate added soil possibly the air permeability has been impaired considerably. The low value of max. dry density may be attributed to this phenomenon in the sticky sodium silicate added soil.

(C) *Permeability test*^{15,17} :

Results of the constant head permeability test on the sedimented samples have been presented in Table 2. The permeability co-efficient of soils is function of various factors and the test is less reproducible than the tests of index properties like Atterberg limits etc. However, the two samples of the sedimented Purulia clay have given almost identical values, the average being, 1.9×10^{-7} cm/s meaning that the soil is impermeable. The result is consistent with the clay percentage of this soil.

The addition of Ca^{2+} (as $CaCl_2$) in the soil has improved the permeability value to some extent²⁷.

The samples added with Na^+ (as $NaCl$ and Na_2SiO_3) have shown less values of permeability co-efficient excepting one sample (with 0.4% Na^+ as $NaCl$) showing higher value compared to the blank soil. As already said that the test is less reproducible. The stray high value may be overlooked and it may be inferred that the addition of Na^+ reduces the permeability, in general.

This inference that calcium added soil is friable, more permeable and aerated in comparison with the sodium added soil (less permeable, sticky) conforms to the general view of the agronomists in this matter. Actually so-

dium causes deflocculation while calcium causes agglomeration and flocculation.

The leaching in the process of sedimentation of salt added soil has caused lowering of concentration of additives from its initial value²⁷. The leaching is pronounced in Ca^{2+} added soils compared to the Na^+ added soils. The flow of water in the permeability test has probably lessened the concentration further.

(D) *Discussion on shear and consolidation test results*^{13,15,18,22,27,34-37}:

(i) *Compacted soil (Tables 3, 4)* :

Sodium silicate is used in sandy soils as a grouting material to seal the pores, the result of which is decrease in permeability and increase in strength. But here the sodium silicate solution is thoroughly mixed with the Purulia clay. The compacted stabilised soil has shown higher shear strength (C_u) and secant modulus, but flexibility (indicated by failure strain) has not been found to be affected much. The C_c (compression index) value has been found marginally increased compared to that of the original soil.

(ii) *Sedimented soil* :

In contrast with the above observations on the compacted soils the results of the sedimented soils with the chemical additives have not shown clear indication of improvement of some engineering properties. The prob-

Table 2. Permeability test results of the sedimented soil

Sample no.	Mixture details	Permeability co-efficient (cm/s) (K) at 27 °C
P-001	Clay blank (Purulia soil)	0.18×10^{-6} Avg. 0.19×10^{-6}
P-002	Clay blank (Purulia soil)	0.20×10^{-6}
P-421	0.4% Na^+ (as $NaCl$) + Purulia soil	1.05×10^{-6}
P-431	1% Na^+ (as $NaCl$) + Purulia soil	0.03×10^{-6}
P-521	0.4% Na^+ (as Na_2SiO_3) + Purulia soil	0.02×10^{-6}

Table 3. Result of the unconfined compression test on the compacted stabilized soil

Sample details	Sample no.	C_u kg/cm ²	E^a kg/cm ²	Failure strain ϵ_f (%)	Moisture content (%)	Dry density (g/cc)	e_0
Purulia soil (blank)	SC-001	1.232	76.85	4.7	17.8	1.680	0.62
Soil + 0.4% Na^+ (Na_2SiO_3)	SC-521	1.555	83.55	4.5	19.9	1.631	0.67

SC stands for shear test of compacted soil.

^aSecant modulus at 1/2 the failure.

Table 4. Result of the consolidation test of the compacted soil from initial state as optimum moisture content (OMC)

Soil details	Sample no.	Moisture content (%)	e_0	$e_0 - e_{6.4}$	C_c at stage 1 ^a	C_c at stage 2 ^b
Purulia soil (blank)	CC-001	16.8	0.61	0.18	0.02	0.25
Soil + 0.4% Na ⁺ (Na ₂ SiO ₃)	CC-521	19.1	0.66	0.17	0.03	0.28

^aStage 1 ⇒ lower load. ^bStage 2 ⇒ higher load.
CC' stands for consolidation test of compacted soil.

able causes are (i) less reproducible test methods, (ii) different phenomena acting simultaneously nullifying individual effects, (iii) low activity of the original clayey soil etc.

Consolidation test (Table 5, Figs. 2A, 2B, 2C) :

In some of the tests the C_c value at lower load range (stage 1) has been found slightly less than that at higher load range (stage 2). Attempts were made (i) to lessen the wall friction of the consolidation mould by using silicon

grease and (ii) to expel entrapped air in the soil slurry by tapping, still probably these could not be achieved fully. These may be among the causes of different values of C_c at different load ranges. The values of C_c (stage 2) of all soil samples have been found to range from 0.305 to 0.410 and the values of individual specimens also vary e.g. the C_c of the blank soil i.e. Purulia clay has been found to range from 0.305 to 0.35.

Overall speaking, the C_c values have been found to

Table 5. Results of the consolidation test of the stabilised soil from initial state as liquid limit

Soil details	Sample no.	Moisture content (%)	e_0	$e_0 - e_{6.4}$	e (from $e - \log p$ curve)	C_c at stage 1	C_c at stage 2
Purulia soil (blank)	C-001	47.0	1.28	0.70	0.96	0.31	0.35
	C-002	47.0	1.28	0.70	0.96	0.31	0.34
	C-003	46.2	1.25	0.75	0.835	0.285	0.305
	C-004	48.4	1.26	0.81	0.845	0.32	0.35
	Avg.	47.2	1.27	0.74	0.90	0.305	0.34
Purulia soil + 0.2% Na ⁺ (as NaCl)	C-411	43.8	1.19	0.69	0.89	0.32	0.35
Purulia soil + 0.4% Na ⁺ (as NaCl)	C-421	44.5	1.205	0.68	0.91	0.285	0.36
Purulia soil + 1% Na ⁺ (as NaCl)	C-431	41.8	1.14	0.68	0.87	0.32	0.34
Purulia soil + 0.2% Na ⁺ (as Na ₂ SiO ₃)	C-511	43.0	1.24	0.60	1.06	0.255	0.39
Purulia soil + 0.4% Na (as Na ₂ SiO ₃)	C-521	40.6	19.1	0.53	1.06	0.20	0.40

Except Purulia soil all other data of stabilized soil are avg. of different specimen.

'C' Stands for consolidation.

Stage 1 ⇒ lower load; Stage 2 ⇒ higher load.

Fig. 2. $e - \log p$ plots of different soil samples consolidated from LL state.

increase with addition of different chemicals. It is astonishing as usually more the liquid limit is, more is the C_c and with admixture the values of LL have been decreased, in general. Again, the change in void ratio from the initial stage (e_0) to that at the highest load of 6.4 kg/cm^2 ($e_{6.4}$) i.e. ($e_0 - e_{6.4}$) has been found less in most cases in the chemically treated soils than in the blank Purulia soil. It simply indicates the higher rate of change of 'e' at the

higher load range.

The C_c has been found nearly the same or slightly higher with NaCl additive, but the value is much higher at the higher load range with addition of Na_2SiO_3 .

In one set of observation (Table 7) it has been found that with sedimentation or consolidation the concentration of additives has been reduced meaning that some of the additives adsorbed loosely on the particle surfaces come out with the drained pore water under the increased load. Under each load increment the concentration is reduced, the soil at higher load is no more the same soil at lower load unlike the case of the blank soil. In practice, it has been noticed that gradual leaching by weathering deteriorates certain engineering properties of the soils stabilized with slaked lime *etc.* The behaviour and their interpretation are similar to the those given earlier²⁷.

Shear test (Table 6, Fig. 3) :

Any change in soil-water system which reduces double layer thickness tends to increase the shear strength of the soil (at a given void ratio). The factors that control the increase in shear strength of clay are (i) increase of electrolyte concentration, (ii) cation exchange from low to high valence, (iii) decrease of pH of the pore fluid, (iv) decrease in water content *etc.*

Fig. 3. Stress-strain plots of soil samples sedimented from LL state under 0.48 kg/cm^2 .

In the sedimented soils mixed with chemical additives, the general tendency of additives is an increase in shear strength. The undrained shear strength of the original soil has been found 0.076 kg/cm^2 , while the values of ' C_u ' of the stabilised soils have been found to range from 0.069 to 0.112 kg/cm^2 . But the secant modulus values of the stabilised soils are 1.89 to 7.80 kg/cm^2 in contrast

Table 6. Result of the unconfined compression tests on the sedimented stabilized soil

Sample details	Sample no.	Starting moisture content (%)	C_u kg/cm ²	E^* kg/cm ²	Failure strain ϵ_r (%)	$e_{0.48}$	Moisture content % at the test time	Dry density g/cc
Purulia soil (blank)	S-001	41.3	0.076	2.45	17.6	1.01	33.7	1.350
	S-002	46.4	0.077	2.98	17.0	0.95	33.8	1.397
	S-003	46.4	0.074	2.74	17.0	0.95	33.8	1.397
	S-004	46.4	0.074	3.10	17.5	0.95	33.8	1.397
	S-005	47.1	0.080	5.03	13.1	0.48	32.6	1.375
	Avg.	S-006	47.1	0.075	3.10	20.0	0.98	32.6
Purulia soil + 0.2% Na ⁺ (NaCl)	S-411	43.6	0.100	2.70	17.6	0.88	29.8	1.447
Purulia soil + 0.4% Na ⁺ (NaCl)	S-421	42.5	0.088	3.56	17.5	0.91	31.7	1.426
Purulia soil + 1% Na ⁺ (NaCl)	S-431	41.0	0.081	3.37	11.0	0.94	34.3	1.405
Purulia soil + 0.4% Na ⁺ (Na ₂ SiO ₃)	S-521	42.6	0.082	2.68	9.9	1.22	42.4	1.223

* Except Purulia soil all other data of stabilized soil are avg. of different specimen.

* Secant modulus at 1/2 the failure. S Stands for shear test of sediment soil.

Table 7. Loss of chemical additives during the process of sedimentation/consolidation

Soil details	Initial conc. (Before consolidation at LL state)	Final conc. (Obtained within the soil mass after complete consolidation)
Soil + 0.4% Na ⁺ (NaCl)	0.4% Na ⁺	0.312% Na ⁺
Soil + 1% Na ⁺ (NaCl)	1% Na ⁺	0.695% Na ⁺

with the value of the blank soil 3.23 kg/cm². So the stabilized soils are stronger but of fluctuating stiffness, so far as this set of test is concerned. The failure strains are more or less similar excepting very low values of the sample S-431 and S-521. The void ratios of the sedimented soils i.e. the $e_{0.48}$ values are more or less similar to the $e_{0.48}$ values computed from the $e - \log p$ curves of the consolidation test done on the same samples indicating that in the sedimentation tank sedimentation in 48 h is sufficient to dissipate almost completely the pore water pressure due to surcharge weight.

With addition of sodium chloride, strength has been increased but higher concentration of additive is not found to be effective. Generally, the starting/moulding moisture of a stabilized soil is lower than that of the original soil and hence sedimented dry density is more. In case of

liquid limit it has been found that beyond certain concentration of additive, the effect is rather lost or different. Similarly in shear strength the result indicates that there is some optimum concentration of additive for the particular clayey soil used.

With sodium silicate, strength has been increased though the dry density is too low and very little consolidation has occurred during sedimentation (starting moisture content is 42.6%, after sedimentation it is 42.4%).

The result of adding salt is double layer depression and the decrease in the value of liquid limit making soil denser and higher strength after sedimentation. But the sodium silicate added soil even being less dense has shown higher strength possibly due to insoluble gel formation. In case of Ca(OH)₂ added soil the cementing effect obtained in the compacted soil has not been found in the

sedimented soil possibly due to the fact that the hydrated forms of the cementing agents are not so effective in creating cementation bonds. Increase in electrolyte concentration and increase in pH have opposing effects in case of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ treated soils²⁷.

The stronger stabilized soils have higher density meaning more number of typical bonds among the particles, the chemical additives possibly contribute marginal cementation bond which is mobilised after much deformation caused on the soil samples. This marginal bond may also contribute to the lower initial value of C_c (compression index) of the stabilised soils (stage 1).

Conclusion :

It is difficult to duplicate the natural process of soil formation in laboratory. Chemical weathering is a long geological process which is not possible to simulate in the laboratory. Moreover, the clay surface phenomena are complex and are function of a large number of complicated factors. Keeping all these things in mind the inferences of the conducted test set may be enlisted below :

(i) Addition of chemicals changes the values of LL to some extent. However, excess concentration of chemicals is not effective. Clay itself (i.e. mineralogy) may be an important factor as the clay particle are negatively charged, cations have a major role in the phenomenon but anion also may have some contribution.

(ii) The co-efficient of permeability is higher in Ca^{2+} added soils than that in Na^+ added soils.

(iii) The ' C_c ' values are higher (at higher load range) than that of the blank soil. It may be due to loss of electrolyte concentration at each load increment.

(iv) The ' C_u ' values are generally higher, firstly due to greater density, C_u and due to possible marginal cementation bond.

(v) Occurrence of leaching in nature may cause reduction in strength.

(vi) Further test with more active clay mineral like bentonite/montmorillonite may help in developing a comprehensive idea in this subject. For shear test, laboratory vane shear test may be adopted and for consolidation test, study of settlement at very low load range in a frictionless mould may give better results.

(vii) $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and Na_2SiO_3 have greater effect on stabilization of soil than CaCl_2 and $\text{NaCl}.\text{SO}_4^{2-}$ is known to have detrimental effect, Ca^{2+} is preferred compared to Na^+ .

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